

The Effect of Online Customer Reviews and Discounts on Purchasing Decisions for Scarlett Body Lotion in The Shopee Marketplace

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 15 March 2024	Government limitations on community activities because of the COVID-19 epidemic influence activities that call for in-person interactions, such as online buying at marketplaces to meet necessities. Researchers are interested in figuring out how much online customer reviews of Scarlett Body Lotion on Shopee Marketplace influence consumers' decisions to buy. This study uses survey research methods in a causal associative manner. The sample number obtained by applying the basic random sampling approach was 97. Methods of gathering data through the distribution of questionnaires. Multiple linear regression and classical assumption and also hypothesis testing are also used in the analysis process. In light of the study's findings, partial
Corresponding Author: Fedianty Augustinah	online customer reviews significantly affected consumers' decisions on purchasing Scarlett Body Lotion, influencing their purchases by 51.3%.
KEYWORDS: Online Customer Review, Discount, Purchase Decision.	

I. INTRODUCTION

Community activities that necessitate in-person gatherings are affected by government restrictions placed on them because of the Covid-19 outbreak. To continue doing things like online meetings, online learning, and online purchasing for necessities, individuals are beginning to adopt digitalization. Online sales in this instance went up, as stated by the BPS (Central Statistics Agency) "Big Data Review of the Impact of Covid-19 2020" report. Amidst this pandemic, online sales surged significantly in comparison to January 2020 sales. From the entire number of online sales at the start of the year to March 2020, there was a 320% increase. The rapid gain is still going stronger; online sales in April 2020 increased by 480% over January 2020. (Noverius Laoli 2020).

The community seeks secondary requirements like care and beauty in addition to fundamental necessities. In the Covid 19 circumstance, when community gatherings are prohibited, many people purchase online on marketplace platforms like Shopee, Tokopedia, Bukalapak, and others to meet their demands. A marketplace is an online media platform that operates on the internet and facilitates trade and transactions between buyers and sellers. Shopee is the marketplace with the most visitors in the third quarter of 2021, according to Databoks. About 134.4 million people visited the platform, up 5.8% from 127 million during the previous quarter. Within the Compass Dashboard's data

Shopee is the platform with the biggest share of sales for beauty products, with market share data for the March–May 2022 period showing that Shopee and Tokopedia had respective market shares of 80.90% and 19.1% for the beauty category. This sector accounted for 50% of all market transactions, yielding the largest sales. Beauty products including body lotion, body soap, scrubs, deodorant, and other hand and foot care are included in the Body Care area. (Joan 2021).

According to internal Kompas data, the Scarlett brand body lotion holds the top spot with a 23.4% market share in Shopee's body lotion sales for the April–June 2022 period. When making a purchase of Scarlett's body lotion online, a few elements are considered, including discounts and online customer reviews. As stated by Kotler and Armstrong (2016:177)

The knowledge gap in earlier studies served as the impetus for this study. based on studies (Riska et al. 2022) claims that factors related to discounts have a major impact on buying decisions; however, study by Putra, et al (2016) reveals conflicting findings. In the study's online customer review variable (Ardianti and Widiartanto 2019) claims that a significant factor influencing decisions to buy comes from the variable of online customer reviews. In the meanwhile, the research (Marine and Philanthropist 2022) demonstrates the contrary outcome, which is that factors influencing The direct influence of online consumer reviews on purchasing

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decisions is minimal. The author is interested in learning how much online customer evaluations and discounts affect Scarlett's decision to buy body lotion on the Shopee marketplace, based on the previously given description.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Purchase Decision

As stated by Tjiptono (2011: 24) Making a purchase involves a consumer identifying their problems, researching potential brands or products, and weighing the pros and disadvantages of each option before deciding which one to buy. As stated by Kotler and Armstrong (2016: 117), Consumer behavior regarding how individuals, groups, or organizations carry out purchasing activities and how goods, services, or experiences might meet needs is reflected in customer purchase decisions. As said by Buchari Alma (2014: 96) Consumer purchase decisions are influenced by a number of factors, including people, procedures, tangible evidence, financial economics, technology, politics, culture, products, prices, locations, and promotions. This helps to shape consumer attitudes toward processing information and drawing conclusions about what products to buy. The indicators utilized to test the variables pertaining to purchase decisions are based on Buchari Alma's opinion (2014:289) in relation to the steps involved in making a decision, including Need Recognition, Information Search, Evaluation of Alternatives, Purchase Decision and also Post Purchase Behavior.

Online Customer Review

As stated by Ningsih (2019: 26), Online customer reviews are a type of assessment provided by prior customers based on data from the evaluation of a product in several areas, allowing customers to learn about the product's quality. Online customer reviews are a component of E-Wom and represent the honest opinions of customers rather than information authored by users in the form of personal postings or adverts. A type of feedback known as an online customer review is provided by actual consumers and is unaffected by marketing or other information. This can be

utilized to learn what customers think about the offered goods or services, as it usually takes the form of personal posts. Because of this, these reviews can be a valuable resource for businesses and customers that want to purchase. (Elwalda 2016) Online customer reviews are one way that customers can uncover pertinent information that can affect their purchasing decisions. (Almana and Mirza 2013). Online customer review characteristics are measured using indicators in accordance with Putri, et al (2016) which include valence, review amount, argument quality, and source reliability.

Discount

According to Suharno and Sutarso (2010: 275), discounts are one way for companies to provide discounts to their customers during a certain period. Discounts can be given in the form of direct reductions on the purchase price, so that customers can enjoy a cheaper price of the product purchased. Discounts are one way that companies often use to attract customers and increase product sales. According to Paul and Olson (2014: 255), discounts / discounts are a long-term strategy that can reduce prices gradually after products are introduced at high prices. Periodic price reductions can help to influence consumers in increasing sales. According to Sutisna (2012: 302), price discount is a decrease from the usual price of a product that is valid for a certain time. The indicator used in measuring the Discount variable uses the opinion of Sutisna (2012: 300) regarding three things that become discount indicators, namely the amount of discount, discount period, and also discount period.

Hypothesis.

H1: It is assumed that the decision to purchase Scarlett body lotion on the Shopee marketplace is strongly influenced by online customer review.

H2: It is assumed that the decision to purchase Scarlett body lotion on the Shopee marketplace is significantly influenced by discounts.

H3: It is assumed that the decision to purchase Scarlett body lotion on the Shopee marketplace is significantly influenced by discounts and online user reviews simultaneously.

The Framework of the Study

Figure 1. Concept Framework
Source: processed by researcher

Information:

- > = Effect of Online Customer review variables X1, Discount X2 to Y simultaneously
- > = Effect of Online Customer review variable X1, Discount X2 to Y partially.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study employed survey research methodology and causal associative quantitative research techniques. The variables in this study are divided into two categories: bound or dependent variables, which in this case are purchase decision variables (Y), as well as independent variables, in this instance being online customer review variables (X1) and discounts (X2). This research was conducted on the Shopee marketplace with samples that match the characteristics needed and the number is determined through the Cochran formula which has the result that the sample is 97 respondents. In this study, questionnaires and observations are the methods used to collect data. Multiple linear regression tests, classical assumption tests, and instrument test data analysis procedures are employed in data analysis. While the conventional assumption tests take the shape of normality, heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, multiple linear regression, and hypothesis testing, validity and reliability tests are the forms that the instrument test takes. The hypothesis test is then carried out using statistical t tests and coefficient of determination (R2) testing.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Description of Respondents

Table 1. Age Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristic		Sum	Percentage (%)
Age	17 – 25	92	94,8
	26 - 35	1	1
	36 - 45	2	2,1
	>45	2	2,1

Source: processed by researcher

Based on the table above, it can be understood that most respondents—92 individuals, or 94.8%—who answered the questionnaire were between the ages of 17 and 25. There were also two respondents, or 2.1%, between the ages of 36 and 45, and between the ages of 26 and 35, and one respondent, or 1%.

Table 2. Gender Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristic		Sum	Percentage (%)
Gender	Man	5	5,2
	Woman	92	94,8
	Sum	97	100

Source: processed by researcher

It is clear from the above table that most respondents—92 individuals, or 94.8%—are female, and the number of respondents who identify as male is 5, or 5.2%.

Table 3. Characteristics of the respondent's work

Characteristic		Sum	Percentage (%)
Work	Entrepreneur / Entrepreneur	9	9.3
	Student / Student	69	72.2
	Civil servants	2	2.1
	Other	16	16.5

Source: processed by researcher

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The above table explains why the majority of respondents—69 individuals, or 72.2%—have the status of students. Next, there are those with other jobs, which indicate statuses other than students, civil servants, and entrepreneurs—16 individuals, or 16.5%—work as entrepreneurs, or 9.3%—and those who work as civil servants (Civil Servants), or 2 individuals, or 2.1%.

Data Analysis

Validity Test

Table 4. Validity Test Results

Variable	Item	R-count	R Table (df = 95)	Information
Online customer review	X1.1	0,896	0,1996	Valid
	X1.2	0,866	0,1996	Valid
	X1.3	0,852	0,1996	Valid
	X1.4	0,767	0,1996	Valid
Discount	X2.1	0,835	0,1996	Valid
	X2.2	0,867	0,1996	Valid
	X2.3	0,862	0,1996	Valid
	X2.4	0,831	0,1996	Valid
	X2.5	0,795	0,1996	Valid
	X2.6	0,900	0,1996	Valid
Purchase Results	Y1.1	0,869	0,1996	Valid
	Y1.2	0,886	0,1996	Valid
	Y1.3	0,800	0,1996	Valid
	Y1.4	0,791	0,1996	Valid
	Y1.5	0,818	0,1996	Valid

Source: processed by researcher

The correlation coefficient (r calculate) for each indicator used to measure the variables in this study is greater than that of the table (r = 0.1996 in this case). All of these signs are therefore deemed valid.

Reliability Test

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Reability Coefficients	Cronbach's Alpha	Critical Value	Information
Online customer review	4 items	0,866	0,600	Reliable
Discount	6 items	0,921	0,600	Reliable
Purchase decision	5 items	0,886	0,600	Reliable

Source: processed author

As can be seen from the above table, all respondents' responses to statements on the variables online customer review (X1), discount (X2), and also purchase decision (Y) are deemed dependable or reliable if their alpha Cronbach's for each variable is more than 0.6.

Normality Test

Figure 2. Normality Test Graph

Source: processed by researcher

The data is not regularly distributed, as the table above demonstrates, because certain patterns do not lie along the diagonal. Thus, the normalcy test using Kolmogorov Smirnov was employed by the researchers.

Table 6. Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		97
Normal	Mean	.0000000
Parameters a,b	Std. Deviation	.36024582
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.063
	Positive	.049
	Negative	-.063
Test Statistic		.063
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200c,d

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.
- c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.
- d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

Source: processed by researcher

The table indicates that the research variables are normally distributed since the significance level is greater than 0.05 and the kolmogorov-smirnov Z value is 0.063 at a significance level of 0.200.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 3. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Source: processed by researcher

Given that the data points in the picture are dispersed throughout the range of 0 to Y and do not follow any particular pattern, the regression model that was created did not find any heteroscedasticity.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 7. Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficient

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Beta	Tolerance
1 (Constant)	1.949	1.259		1.548	.125		
TOTAL_X1	.606	.105	.463	5.793	.000	.682	1.465
TOTAL_X2	.309	.061	.407	5.092	.000	.682	1.465

a. Dependent Variable: TOTAL_Y1

Source: processed by researcher

The variables online customer review (X1) and discount (X2) are known to have a tolerance value of more than 0.1 and a VIF lower than 10, which suggests that multicollinearity was not present in this inquiry, according to the table above.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 8. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Coefficient

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Beta	Tolerance
1 (Constant)	1.949	1.259		1.548	.125		
TOTAL_X1	.606	.105	.463	5.793	.000	.682	1.465
TOTAL_X2	.309	.061	.407	5.092	.000	.682	1.465

a. Dependent Variable: TOTAL_Y1

Source: processed by researcher

The multiple linear regression equation that was obtained from the earlier table is as follows:

$$Y = 1.949 + 0.606(X1) + 0.309(X2)$$

The multiple linear regression equation can be interpreted as follows: 1.949 is the constant value. This shows that if the coefficients for the online customer review (X1) and discount (X2) are present, the consistent value of the purchase choice (Y) is 1.949. Then, the regression coefficient of 0.606 for the online customer review variable (X1) means that the purchase decision (Y) will increase by 0.606 units for every 1% increase in online customer reviews (X1). The positive value of the regression coefficient leads one to the conclusion that online customer reviews (X1) have a beneficial influence on purchasing decisions (Y). Furthermore, the Purchase Decision (Y) will increase by 0.309 units for every 1% increase in the Discount Variable (X2), according to the latter's regression coefficient of 0.309. The fact that the regression coefficient is positive suggests that Discount (X2) influences Purchase Decision (Y) in a positive way. Finally, it is also clear that the online customer review (X1) is 5,793 and the discount (X2) is 5,092. To put it another way, the t-count value of the online customer review (X1) and discount (X2) is 1.985 over the t-table. With an online customer review (X1) significance of 0.000 and a discount (X2) of 0.000 < chance of 0.005. Thus, it can be said that H0 was turned down and H1 was approved, indicating that "Scarlett's body lotion purchase decision on the Shopee Marketplace is significantly influenced by online customer reviews and discounts."

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Hypothesis Test

Table 9. Test Results t Coefficient

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
1 (Constant)	1.949	1.259		1.548	.125
TOTAL_X1	.606	.105	.463	5.793	.000
TOTAL_X2	.309	.061	.407	5.092	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TOTAL_Y1

Source: processed by researcher

If, as the following table shows, the Online Customer Review Variable (X1) has a t-count of 5.793 > t-table 1.985 with a significant level of 0.000 < 0.005, then the first hypothesis (H1) has a substantial influence. Thus, it may be said that Purchase Decisions (Y) are significantly improved by the Online Customer Review variable (X1). The t-count is 5.092 > t-table 1.968 with a significant level of 0.000 < 0.005 if the second hypothesis (H2) for the Discount variable (X2) has a significant influence. Thus, it can be concluded that the Discount variable (X2) has a major influence on improving Purchase Decisions (Y). The variable that significantly influences Purchase Decision (Y) is the Online customer review (X1), with a t-count value of 5.793 > t-calculate Discount (X2) 5.092. Therefore, the most important factor affecting decisions to buy is online customer reviews (Y). Based on the test results, which included online user evaluations and discounts on Scarlett's decision to buy body lotion on the Shopee marketplace, it can be said that Ha was approved.

Table 10. Results of the coefficient of partial determination Coefficient

Model	Correlations		
	Zero-order	Partial	Part
1 (Constant)			
TOTAL_X1	.692	.513	.382
TOTAL_X2	.667	.465	.336

a. Dependent Variable: TOTAL_Y1

Source: processed by researcher

The partial correlation value between the online customer review variable (X1) and the purchase decision (Y) is 0.513, or 51.3%, according to Table 10 of the coefficient of determination analysis results (r2). However, there is a 46.5%, or 0.465, partial correlation between the purchase

choice (Y) and the discount variable (X2). The aim of this study was to investigate the potential simultaneous effects of two independent factors, namely the discount (X2) and online customer reviews (X1), on the variable associated with the purchase decision (Y). The test criteria are as follows:

Table 11. F Test Results

ANOVA					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	291.806	2	145.903	67.941	.000b
Residual	201.864	94	2.147		
Total	493.670	96			

a. Dependent Variable: Y

b. Predictors: (Constant), X2, X1

Source: processed by researcher

The table above displays the concurrent results of the F-test. At a significant level of 0.000, the F-count value is 67.941. However, the F-table value is 3.09. The F-count value is 67.941 >, the F-table is 3.09, and the significance level is 0.000 < 0.005. Consequently, it can be concluded that elements influencing purchase decisions (Y) are significantly influenced in a positive way by both online customer reviews (X1) and discounts (X2). Test Coefficient of Determination (R2): This coefficient of determination measures how much the two independent variables—the online customer review (X1) and the discount (X2)—influence the dependent variable, the decision to make a purchase. The following table illustrates this:

Table 12. Test Results of Simultaneous Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary				
Model	R	Adjusted R Square	R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.769a	.591	.582	1.465

a. Predictors: (Constant), X2, X1

b. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: processed by researcher

According to Table 12, the R Square value obtained from the coefficient of determination (R2) analysis was 0.591, or 59.1%. Discounts and online customer reviews are two independent variables that simultaneously affect the dependent variable, the choice to make a purchase. The remaining 40.9% were influenced by factors other than the ones this study looked at.

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The Influence of Online Customer Reviews on Scarlett's Body Lotion Purchase Decision on the Shopee marketplace

The decision to buy Scarlett body lotion on the Shopee marketplace is influenced by online user reviews. A table t of 1.985 and a calculated t value of 5.793 both support this. This indicates that significant values of $0.000 < 0.05$ correspond to t counts $>$ t table. 51.3%, or 0.513, is the positive value of the regression coefficient. Study findings indicate that decisions to buy Scarlett body lotion on the Shopee marketplace are positively and significantly influenced by online customer reviews. This indicates that positive online customer reviews left by previous users may influence beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors when making judgments about what to buy online.

The Effect of Discounts on Scarlett's Body Lotion Purchase Decision on the Shopee marketplace

The decision to purchase Scarlett body lotion on the Shopee marketplace is influenced by discounts. A table t of 1.985 and a computed t value of 5.092 both support this. This indicates that significant values of $0.000 < 0.05$ correspond to t counts $>$ t table. At 46.5%, or 0.465, the regression coefficient is positive. The findings of the study show that discounts have a positive and significant influence on customers' decisions to buy Scarlett body lotion on the Shopee platform. This implies that reductions offered by Shopee marketplace merchants may pique customers' interest in making purchases online.

The Influence of Online Customer Reviews and Discounts on Scarlett's Body Lotion Purchase Decision on the Shopee marketplace

Customer Reviews on the Internet Scarlett's body lotion purchasing decision on Shopee is influenced by discounts, as evidenced by a table with a 3.09 score and an F calculate value of 67.941. F counts $>$ F table with significant values of $0.000 < 0.05$, according to this. At 0.591, or 59.1%, the coefficient of determination is positive. The study's findings indicate that Scarlett's body lotion purchases made on the Shopee marketplace are significantly influenced favorably by both discounts and online customer evaluations. This includes demonstrating how favorable online customer evaluations and discounts from prior clients can influence consumers' confidence, attitudes, and purchasing patterns.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

Based on the research and discussion, it can be concluded that Scarlett's decisions to purchase body lotion on Shopee are influenced by online customer reviews and discounts. These factors either partially or simultaneously have a positive and significant impact on Scarlett's decisions to purchase body lotion. Numerous tests that have been carried

out to confirm the accuracy of the existing theories serve as evidence for this.

Suggestion

The suggestion from the research that has been done is in the form of providing discounts and developing online customer reviews on Shopee in accordance with the intended target, in this case women with an age range of 17-25 years as the most users of the Shopee marketplace. Furthermore, Shopee can also encourage customers to leave a review after making a purchase and then provide incentives for it. In addition, Shopee can also provide varied discounts, ranging from different types of discounts, discount times, and the number of discounts on Shopee. Some of these recommendations are given to improve customer purchase decisions on the Shopee marketplace.

REFERENCES

1. Alma, Bukhari. 2014. *Manajemen Pemasaran Dan Pemasaran Jasa*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
2. Almana, A., dan A. Mirza. 2013. “The Impact of Electronic Word of Mouth on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions.” *International Journal of Computer Applications* Vol. 82, N.
3. Ardianti, Asri Nugrahani, dan M. A. Widiartanto. 2019. “Pengaruh Online Customer Review Dan Online Customer Rating Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Melalui Marketplace Shopee .” *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis* 1–11.
4. Bahari, Moh Fajar, dan Rizky Dermawan. 2022. “Pengaruh Online Customer Review Dan Online Customer Rating Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Pada Aplikasi Tokopedia Di Kecamatan Tanjunganom Kabupaten Nganjuk.” *Seiko* 100–108. doi: 10.37531/sejaman.v5i2.2109.
5. Elwalda, Abdulaziz. 2016. “The Impact of Online Customer Reviews (OCRs) on Customers ' Purchase Decision.” 44(0):0–55.
6. Jerry C. Olson dan Peter J. Paul. 2014. *Perilaku Konsumen Dan Strategi Pemasaran*. Edisi Semb. Jakarta.: Penerbit Salemba Empat.
7. Joan, Valerie. 2021. “Produk Kecantikan Tembus Transaksi 20 Miliar, Brand Lokal Terfavorit.” *Compas*. Retrieved (<https://compas.co.id/article/penjualan-produk-kecantikan/>).
8. Kotler, dan Armstrong. 2016. *Principles of Marketing*. Jakarta: Person Education Limited.
9. Ningsih, dan Sri Putri Eliska. 2019. “Pengaruh Rating Dan Online Customer Review Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Secara Online Pada MarketplaceShopee.” *Skripsi, Fakultas Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Jurusan Manajemen Universitas Muhammadiyah. Makasar*.

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10. Noverius Laoli. 2020. “BPS Catat Penjualan Online Melonjak Tajam Selama Pandemi Corona.” *Kontan.Co.Id*. Retrieved September 3, 2022 (<https://nasional.kontan.co.id/news/bps-catat-penjualan-online-melonjak-tajam-selama-pandemi-corona>).
11. Putri, Latifa, and Harimukti Wandebori. 2016. “Factors Influencing Cosmetics Purchase Intention In Indonesia Based On Online Review.” *International Conference on Ethics of Business, Economics, dan Social Science (ICEBEES)* 255–63.
12. Riska, Cindy Febya, Ilmi Nabilah, Julietha Lindasari, dan Putri Disty Kholipah. 2022. “Pengaruh Diskon Dan Promosi Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian.” (August):18.
13. Suharno dan Yudi Sutarso. 2010. *Marketing In Practice*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
14. Sutisna. 2012. *Perilaku Konsumen Dan Komunikasi Pemasaran*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rusdakarya.
15. Tjiptono, Fandy. 2011. *Strategi Pemasaran*. Edisi III. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.